

MEAN-FIELD BASED FATIGUE DAMAGE MODELING OF COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH SHORT STRAIGHT AND WAVY FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a micro-mechanics based modelling approach is proposed for predicting the quasi-static and fatigue behaviour of short random fiber reinforced composites. Two types of short fiber micro-structures are considered, namely the typical short straight fiber composites, in addition to wavy fiber micro-structures. Different algorithms of the proposed approach are described and validated including: a model for extension of mean-field homogenization methods for wavy fiber composites, models for description of the non-linear quasi-static behaviour of the short fiber composites and finally a novel fatigue model for prediction of the S-N behaviour of short fiber composites based on the S-N curve of the constituents.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fiber composites are attractive materials due to their combination of high stiffness, low weight characteristics as well as their rapid low-cost production especially with injection molding techniques. While composites reinforced with short straight fibers such as glass and carbon fibers are well known in literature, short wavy fibers such as steel fibers are less commonly known. Steel fibers are outstanding fibers combining high stiffness properties together with high ductility.

This work presents a methodology for micro-mechanics based modelling of the quasi-static and fatigue behaviour of the short fiber composites in the frame-work of mean-field homogenization techniques, namely the Mori-Tanaka model. The methodology is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Proposed methodology for micro-mechanics based modeling of short steel fiber composites based on input of lifetime cyclic behavior of pure matrix, fiber and interface.

The present work considers both the typical straight short fiber composites as well as wavy short fiber composites. Waviness can be found in composites with high aspect ratios of the fiber or can be an

inherent characteristic of some fiber materials, e.g. natural fibers. In this work, steel fiber reinforced composites are considered as an example of wavy fiber composites. These kind of materials have been developed for their attractive shielding properties. The materials are currently being investigated as reinforcements for structural applications. A characteristic of the injection molded steel fiber composites of the present investigation is the high waviness of the micron-sized fibers embedded in the matrix. The paper present an overall description of the proposed models in addition to validation of the models on a number of test cases.

2 THE MORI-TANAKA APPROACH

In modeling fiber reinforced composites, a class of models exists which is based on Eshelby [1] solution for ellipsoidal inclusions, from which several mean field averaging schemes are derived for different types of materials. Among those schemes, the Mori-Tanaka method [2] is the most popular especially for the micro-mechanical modeling of sheet molded compounds (SMC), particle reinforced composites, and random fiber reinforced composites.

For straight fiber composite systems, fibers (inclusions) are approximated by generalized ellipsoids, for which the dilute Eshelby solution is known either analytically or numerically.

Using the Mori-Tanaka formulation, the effective composite stiffness can be calculated as shown in Equation 1

$$C^{eff} = C^m + \sum_{\alpha=1}^M c_{\alpha} (C^{\alpha} - C^m) A^{\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where C^{eff} is the composite effective stiffness, C^m and C^{α} are the stiffness of matrix and inclusion respectively, A^{α} is the strain concentration tensor which relates the strain inside of the inclusion to the macroscopic applied strain, c_{α} is the volume fraction of individual inclusions. The inclusion and matrix strain concentration tensor A^{α} and A_m^{α} can be calculated as in Equation 2, where $S^{\alpha\alpha}$ is the Eshelby tensor.

$$A^{\alpha} = A_m^{\alpha} \left(\sum_{\beta=1}^M c_{\beta} A_m^{\beta} \right)^{-1} \quad A_m^{\alpha} = [I + S^{\alpha\alpha} (C^m) (C^{\alpha} - C^m)]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Nevertheless, for more complex composite structures such as short random steel fiber composites, the fibers are curved (wavy) and the derivation of the Eshelby solution becomes mathematically complex. In this respect, a model is needed for the transformation of wavy fibers into an equivalent ellipsoidal inclusions system for which mathematical formulations are readily available.

3 THE POLY-INCLUSION MODEL (P-I) FOR EXTENSION OF THE M-T APPROACH TO WAVY FIBER COMPOSITES

The P-I model is a proposed model for the extension of Mori-Tanaka formulation to the case of wavy fibers composites. In the P-I model, each wavy fiber is subdivided into a sufficiently large number of small segments. The original yarn segments are replaced by equivalent ellipsoidal inclusions such that the average stress and strain states in both the original segment and the ellipsoid are the same. In that way, available mean field approaches based on Eshelby solution for ellipsoidal inclusions can be readily used. The aspect ratio of the equivalent ellipsoid is a function of the local fiber curvature.

Using a simple mathematical formulation, Huysmans et al. [3] presented the relationship between local curvature and equivalent ellipsoid aspect ratio as given by Equation 3.

$$b = \beta * R \quad (3)$$

Where b is the elongation (length) of the equivalent ellipsoid, R is the local radius of curvature of the segment (Figure 2). Factor β is the proportionality between both parameters. As indicated by Equation (6.1), segments with higher local curvatures are modeled with equivalent inclusions with lower aspect ratios, reflecting lower efficiency of curved segment.

Huysmans et al. [3] performed an analysis for the evaluation of β factor for the highly curved yarns in knitted fabric composites and found that the best correlation with experimentally measured stiffness of the composite is obtained with β “lying around 3”, and the chosen value was $\beta = \pi$. It should be noted that in the range $\beta = 1.5 \dots 3$ the influence of the choice of β value on the stiffness of the composite is weak (difference in the stiffness values below 5%).

Figure 2 Equivalent ellipsoid replacing the original curved fiber segment [3].

4 DESCRIPTION OF THE NON-LINEAR DAMAGE MODEL

When subjected to loading, short fiber reinforced composites exhibit a non-linear stress-strain behavior. This also applies to all the straight and wavy fiber reinforced materials investigated in the present work. The sources of non-linearities can be attributed to the non-linear elasto-plastic behavior of the polymer matrix and the damage development in the composite. This section presents the formulation of the proposed matrix plasticity and damage models namely the fiber-matrix debonding and fiber breakage, in the framework of mean-field homogenization models.

4.1 Matrix non-linearity

the Eshelby based mean-field homogenization models, including the M-T method used in this work, can only be used for composites with linear-elastic constituents. To overcome this, the concept of the “reference” material is introduced. In the secant approach, the weakening constraint power of the matrix as a result of its plastic deformation is represented by the evolution of its secant modulus using the well-known approach of Tandon and Weng [4].

The yielding matrix (with a prescribed elasto-plastic behavior) is then replaced at each load step with a linear elastic reference material having the same secant properties of the matrix during this load step.

The non-linear plastic behavior of the matrix is modelled using a von Mises criterion together with an associated flow rule. An isotropic hardening flow rule is adopted in the present work, represented by the modified Ludwik equation (Equation 4). This was found to accurately fit the non-linear stress-strain behavior of all of the thermoplastic matrices considered in this work.

$$\sigma^* = \sigma_y + h (\varepsilon^{p*})^n \quad (4)$$

Where σ^* is the effective (von Mises) stress in the matrix, ε^{p*} is the effective matrix plastic strain, and σ_y , h and n are the initial yield stress, strength coefficient and work hardening exponent respectively.

The secant Young's modulus E_m^s and Poisson's coefficient at a given effective plastic strain ε^{p*} is computed as follows:

$$E_m^s = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{E_m} + \frac{\varepsilon^{p*}}{\sigma^*}} \quad (5)$$

$$v_m^s = \frac{1}{2} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - v_m\right) \frac{E_m^s}{E_m} \quad (6)$$

3.1 Fiber-matrix debonding

Damage is another main source of the non-linear deformation behavior of short fiber composites. The main damage mechanism of short fiber composites is failure of the interface which results in debonding of the fibers from the embedding matrix and hence a degradation in the load carrying capability of the fibers.

A partially debonded isotropic inclusion is replaced by a perfectly bonded segment with degraded anisotropic stiffness properties degraded by the damage variables along the interface of debonded fiber and distinguishing between percentage of debonded surfaces loaded in tension or compression. To achieve that, three distinct micro-mechanical variables (d , γ , δ) are assigned to each inclusion (Figure 3)

- γ : total amount of the debonded interface area which is loaded on traction.
- δ : percentage of the frictional sliding interface, i.e. relative amount of the of the debonded interface area which loaded in compression.

These parameters can then be computed for each inclusion from the local interfacial stress states (discussed in the previous section) along the equator of the inclusion. An example is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Schematic representation of the debonding model and an example of the estimation of the damage parameters.

3.2 Fiber-breakage

fiber breakage is rarely found in short fiber composites as in these types of composites only a limited probability of the fibers are longer than the critical length and/or depict weak interface with the embedding, thus favoring the debonding damage mechanism. Nevertheless, in the implementation of the damage models in the present work, a criterion for fiber breakage is assigned as follows:

$$\sigma_{33}^{\alpha} \geq \sigma_{ult}^f \quad (7)$$

The criterion in Equation (7) assumes that breakage of the inclusion occurs when the axial stress state (defined in the inclusion local coordinate system) in the inclusion is higher than the ultimate strength of the corresponding fiber material. In this work, the broken inclusion is replaced by a void, i.e. with a null equivalent stiffness tensor $C_{ij}^{eq} = 0$.

4 DESCRIPTION OF THE FATIGUE MODEL

In the present work, a model is developed for predicting the fatigue S-N behavior of short fiber composites based on the S-N curves of the constituents in the framework of mean-field homogenization methods. By knowledge of the S-N behavior of the fibers and the matrix, failure criteria can be assigned to predict the final failure of the composite. The failure criteria are assigned below:

$$\langle \sigma_{11}^f \rangle = X^f \quad (8)$$

$$\langle \sigma_*^m \rangle = X^m \quad (9)$$

X^f and X^m are fatigue failure functions of the fibers and matrix respectively which reflect the fatigue strength of the constituent at a given fatigue life. The first equation denote fiber failure while the second equation denote the failure of the matrix.

In contrast to unidirectional and textile composites, failure of a fiber in the short composite does not lead to failure of the composite. In contrast, failure of the matrix directly results in overall failure of the composite. In this respect, Equation is considered the main failure criterion in the fatigue model.

Another interesting aspect of this work, is introducing the effect of the fatigue of the interface. It has been shown in previous literature that short fiber composite exhibit a decrease in interface strength due to fatigue loading or the so-called "fatigue of the interface". The behavior was confirmed by different authors e.g. who investigated the fracture surface of tensile and fatigue tested samples and reported that the fatigue failed samples showed much higher debonding rates and probabilities of pull-out. In this respect an addition failure criterion reflecting the S-N curve of the interface can be described as follows:

$$\sigma_c^i = X^i \quad (10)$$

Where σ_c^i is the critical interface strength of an inclusion i and X^i reflect the S-N curve of the interface.

Nevertheless, an experimental characterization of the fatigue of interface is a very difficult undertaking. This requires performed complex pull-out or fragmentation tests under cyclic loading. For this reason the S-N curve of the interface need to be estimated.

In this work, an estimate of the S-N curve of the interface is suggested to be the same as the S-N curve of the matrix. This is based on the assumption that the interface is matrix dominated. A parametric study is performed to show the effect of different slopes of the S-N curves of the interface on the predictions of the fatigue model.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Poly-Inclusion approach

In the first test case, a volume element (VE) containing a single half circular fiber is considered (Figure 4 (a)). The fiber has a constant curvature k of 0.1. Three different models with fiber volume fraction $VF = 14.7\%$, 5.29% and 2.35% are considered; VF is varied by variation of the fiber diameters.

Figure 4 Test cases for models of wavy fibres composites: (a) circular arc fibre (b) random fibres from micro CT image.

In the second test case a VE contains wavy steel fibers extracted from micro-CT scans of steel fiber reinforced composites (Figure 4 (b)). Details of the micro-CT scans and of the geometry of the VE can be found in [5]. The considered VE includes 30 fibers which has been previously reported as the sufficient number of inclusions to form a VE of random fibers [6]. The diameter of all fibers was set to $d = 8 \mu m$ which is the nominal diameter given in the fibers datasheet [7]. The fiber volume fraction of the VE containing 30 fibers is the same as of the scanned composite sample. The objective of this test case is the validation of the P-I model on fibers with non-uniform random waviness and to verify the accuracy of the P-I model in predicting local stress fields in case of fiber interactions.

Figure 5 shows the results of modelling of the first test case. The value of $\beta = \pi/2$ best correlated with the overall elastic properties and the local stresses in inclusions for this test case. The predictions of the P-I model converge with increase of the number of segments starting from the value of $N_{segments} = 5$. The trends of analytical P-I model correspond to the trends of FE simulations of equivalent inclusions. The discrepancies between predictions of analytical P-I model and real stress fields in wavy fibre is due to loss of connectivity of equivalent segments.

Figure 5 Comparison of P-I model predictions of average local stresses σ_{33} in equivalent inclusions of the first test case (half circular fibre): (a) with variations of number of segments; (b) different volume fractions.

Figure 6 shows the predictions of the P-I model compared to FEA for the second test case. For all fibres, 20 segments were used. For clarity, an example of two fibres with exact matching of segments between P-I and FEA is shown. Figure 6(a) shows that the P-I model gives very good agreement with FEA for segments axial stresses. In this case, generally, an efficiency factor of $\beta = \pi/2$ gives the best matching with experimental data.

To summarize, it has been shown that the P-I model generally gives good agreement of the homogenized global elastic response of VEs of wavy fibres as well as local stress fields in inclusions. Predictions of axial stress states in equivalent inclusions depicted very good agreement with FE results. Trends of normal stress states in equivalent inclusions showed less agreement with FE results in cases of fibres with variable local curvatures. Nevertheless, overall predicted values were still within reasonable accuracy. The obtained local stress and strain fields are the basis for the developed progressive damage model for the prediction of the non-linear behaviour of the short wavy fiber composites.

4.2 Non-linear quasi-static damage model

The overall solution scheme starts with modelling the geometry of each type of material. Based on the micro-structural parameters discussed above for each distinct material, a representative volume element is generated using the model described in [5]. The next step in the solution is the translation of the generated fiber information to an inclusion system. This step distinguishes between straight and wavy fiber composites. In the straight fiber composites the fibers and inclusions are interchangeable, where one fiber is directly considered an ellipsoidal inclusion with the same aspect ratio as the original generated fiber. In the case of the wavy fiber composites the P-I model is used to discretize a wavy fiber into a number of segments which are then replaced with equivalent ellipsoidal inclusions with elongations (aspect ratios) obtained from the relationship in Equation (3). An inclusion then represents a segment of the wavy fibers.

Figure 6 Comparison of P-I model predictions of average local stresses in equivalent inclusions of the third test case (VE of real fibers) against full FEA. The figure shows the comparison for an example of two selected fibers from the VE for (a) for axial segment stresses σ_{33} and (b) for transverse segment stresses σ_{22} of 10 fibers in the modelled VE.

Finally, based on the properties of the constituents, and the suitable damage parameters, the quasi-static non-linear simulation can be performed on the representative inclusion system.

The non-linear damage models are applied on two glass fiber reinforced systems namely: a 30 weight% short glass fiber reinforced Polyamide 6 and a 30 weight% short glass fiber reinforced polypropylene composite. The composites will be denoted GF-PA and GF-PP respectively. Table 1 summarized the input parameters for the non-linear model for both materials.

Table 1 Summary of the micro-structural parameters of the GF-PA and the GF-PP materials of the present work used as input for validation of the developed models.

	GF-PA	GF-PP
Volume Fraction, $V_f\%$	16	13
Fiber length distribution, ψ_L	Lognormal dist. ($\mu = 5.6, \sigma = 0.5$)	Lognormal dist. ($\mu = 6.8, \sigma = 0.7$)
Fiber orientation	$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.77 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.16 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.07 \end{bmatrix}$	$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.86 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.12 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.02 \end{bmatrix}$

Similarly, the models are applied to wavy steel fiber systems with different fiber volume fractions. The materials will be denoted SF-PA. Table 2 summarizes the input parameters of the model for the steel fiber composites. The detailed length distribution of the steel fiber composite materials was not available. Instead a mean value was used to describe the length of the fibers in the RVE.

Table 2 Summary of the micro-structural parameters of the SF-PA materials of the present work used as input for validation of the developed models.

	SF-PA	
Volume Fraction, $V_f\%$	0.5	2
Fiber length distribution, ψ_L	Constant $L = 605 \mu\text{m}$	Constant $L = 557 \mu\text{m}$
Fiber orientation	$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.71 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.18 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.11 \end{bmatrix}$	$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.85 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.02 \end{bmatrix}$

For each material, a comparison of the predicted stress-strain curves of the modelling approach by taking into account only matrix plasticity and the combined matrix plasticity and inclusions damage models are shown and compared to the experimental curves. This is to show the significance of the effect of each non-linear mechanism in the short fiber reinforced composites.

Error! Reference source not found. (a) and (b) shows the simulated stress-strain behavior compared to the experimental curve for the GF-PA and the GF-PP respectively. As can be seen from the figure both matrix plasticity and damage contribute to the non-linear stress-strain behavior of the composite. The non-linearity due to fiber-matrix debonding is however more pronounced, reflecting the significance of damage in short fiber composites. The figure also shows that the overall modelling approach with consideration of both plasticity and damage leads to accurate predictions compared to the experimental curve.

Figure **Error! No text of specified style in document.** Comparison of the experimental and predicted stress-strain behavior of (a) the GF-PA and (b) the GF-PP composite.

Validation of the developed models was similarly performed on the steel fiber composites as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Comparison of the experimental and predicted stress-strain behavior of the (a) SF-PA 0.5VF% and (b) SF-PA 2VF% composites.

Similar to the glass fiber materials, the overall approach was found to give good match of the simulated stress-strain curves compared to the experimental curves for the steel fiber composites. The good predictions compared to the experimental stress-strain behavior validates both the damage modelling approach as well the Poly-Inclusion models for dealing with wavy fibers in Esheby based models.

4.3 Fatigue model

Figures 9 and 10 show the prediction of the S-N curves of the GF-PA and the GF-PP, described above respectively. As previously discussed, in the present model, the slope S-N curve of the interface strength is taken to be the same as the slope of the S-N curve of the pure matrix. The figure shows that this estimation leads to good predictions of the S-N curves of the composite compared to the experimental curves. In principle, the slope of the S-N curve of the interface can be lower than that of the matrix. This corresponds to the case of faster fatigue degradation of the interface compared to that of the pure matrix.

Figure 9 Comparison of the experimental and predicted S-N curves of the GF-PA material.

Similar to the glass fiber materials, the overall approach was found to give good match of the simulated stress-strain curves compared to the experimental curves for the steel fiber composites. The good predictions compared to the experimental stress-strain behavior validates both the damage modelling approach as well the Poly-Inclusion models for dealing with wavy fibers in Esheby based models.

Figure 10 Comparison of the experimental and predicted S-N curves of the GF-PP material.

A parametric study shows the effect of variation of the S-N curve of the interface strength. It can be seen that for both materials, the assumption of zero slope of the interface strength, i.e. no fatigue degradation of the interface leads to a very high estimation of the composite fatigue life. Similarly a high slope of the fatigue of the interface leads to underestimations of the fatigue life of the composite.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A micro-mechanics based modelling approach was developed for the prediction of the quasi-static non-linear stress-strain behavior and the fatigue behavior of short fiber reinforced composites. The models were found to provide good predictions of the stress-strain and S-N behavior of a number of straight and wavy fiber short fiber composites.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Eshelby JD. The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problems 1957.
- [2] Mori T, Tanaka K. Average stress in matrix and average elastic energy of materials with misfitting inclusions. *Acta Metallurgica*. 1973;21(5):571-4.
- [3] Huysmans G, Verpoest I, Van Houtte P. A poly-inclusion approach for the elastic modelling of knitted fabric composites. *Acta Materialia*. 1998;46(9):3003-13.
- [4] Tandon GP, Weng GJ. A Theory of Particle-Reinforced Plasticity. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*. 1988;55(1):126-35.
- [5] Abdin Y, Lomov SV, Jain A, van Lenthe GH, Verpoest I. Geometrical characterization and micro-structural modeling of short steel fiber composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2014;67(0):171-80.
- [6] Pierard O, González C, Segurado J, Llorca J, Doghri I. Micromechanics of elasto-plastic materials reinforced with ellipsoidal inclusions. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*. 2007;44(21):6945-62.
- [7] Bekaert. Beki-Shield stainless steel fibers: efficient filler materials for conductive plastics. Product manual. 2013.